

H63D Syndrome Research Consortium

Physician's Quick Guide: Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type-3) A Rare but Life-Threatening Condition

Reviewed and approved by:
H63D Research Consortium
H63D Research Team Adams
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Oshtoran Syndrome (scientifically known as H63D Syndrome Type-3) is a very rare but insidious and potentially life-threatening multisystem disease. Patients often appear significantly healthier than they actually are, which can be dangerously misleading. The consequences of this syndrome cannot be detected by ordinary laboratory tests or standard imaging. Nevertheless, patients, especially those over 40 years of age, are in constant danger. This guideline is intended to quickly and effectively inform physicians who unexpectedly encounter Oshtoran Syndrome.

Basic Pathophysiology

Oshtoran Syndrome is a complex meta-syndrome that includes the following components:

1. Initial immunological damage (usually in adolescence)
2. Activation of a homozygous HFE H63D mutation with accumulation of toxic NTBI iron with disseminated subclinical inflammations that can only be detected histopathologically. These inflammations can be transient or persist and structurally and/or functionally damage an organ. The only laboratory value that indicates the acute level of inflammatory activity caused by NTBI iron is the kynurenine metabolism, including the KYN/TRY ratio.
3. PDH mitochondriopathy as a result of NTBI accumulation
4. Severe autonomic dysfunction of the general and central nervous system
5. Variable dysfunction of the innate immune system

Central to the pathogenesis is a homozygous mutation of the HFE gene H63D, which leads to an accumulation of NTBI. This results in oxidative stress, organ damage, and a cascade of dysfunctions affecting vital systems.

It is of utmost importance to understand that any change in the established treatment can have fatal consequences.

Oshtoran Syndrome is not only rare but also extremely dangerous. Patients with this disease are in a fragile systemic balance that can be quickly disturbed by medical interventions. In particular, discontinuing or reducing the sometimes unusual-appearing medication can lead to a complete breakdown of body-wide homeostasis and thus to the death of the patient within a few hours.

What to do?

If you do not have the necessary medications available, contact the relatives or caregivers, who are usually trained in dealing with the disease in diagnosed patients.

Oshtoran patients and their social environment are thoroughly educated about the disease, its risks, and the correct treatment after diagnosis. Never be misled by the vital-looking appearance of the patients. The Oshtoran Syndrome is still there.

NEVER change the existing medication of an Oshtoran patient without first talking to and coordinating with them, their family, or the treating specialist.

Clinical Presentation

The symptomatology is highly variable and can affect any organ system:

- Severe autonomic dysregulation ranging from mild to vitally significant (life-threatening) organ dysfunctions
- Neurodegenerative symptoms similar to non-motor Parkinson's symptoms

- Extreme hypersympathicotonia with a tendency to acute vital crises
- Psychiatric and neurological symptoms of organic origin
- Degeneration of ANS, nerve tracts, glands, gonads, etc.
- Cardiovascular symptoms up to sudden cardiac death
- Hepatic changes with steatosis (NAFLD) and nodular hyperplasias (FNH)

NTBI: The Critical, Often Overlooked Factor

IMPORTANT: Many physicians are not familiar with the concept of non-transferrin-bound iron (NTBI). This is a serious problem, as NTBI plays a central role in the pathophysiology of Oshtoran Syndrome.

- NTBI occurs when transferrin saturation rises above 50%.
- Unlike ferritin-bound iron, NTBI is highly reactive and toxic to tissues.
- NTBI cannot be detected by usual iron tests and is completely "silent" in imaging and histopathology (exception B-mode TCS).
- Iron reduction therapies such as phlebotomy or chelators are ineffective and vitally dangerous in NTBI excess.

WARNING:

Phlebotomies or chelation therapies are strictly contraindicated in Oshtoran Syndrome unless ferritin is elevated. However, elevated ferritin practically excludes Oshtoran Syndrome. These treatments can rapidly lead to life-threatening iron deficiency in Oshtoran patients without reducing the harmful NTBI.

Basic Pathophysiology

Oshtoran Syndrome is a complex meta-syndrome that includes the following components:

1. Initial immunological trigger (usually in adolescence)
2. H63D Syndrome Type-1 symptomatology
3. PDH mitochondriopathy as a result of NTBI accumulation
4. Severe autonomic dysfunction of the general and central nervous system
5. Dysfunction of the innate immune system

Central to the pathogenesis is a homozygous mutation of the HFE gene H63D, which leads to an accumulation of NTBI. This results in oxidative stress, organ damage, and a cascade of dysfunctions affecting vital systems.

Therapy

Treatment requires a highly individualized, multidisciplinary approach:

1. Pharmacological intervention:
 - High-dose opiates and benzodiazepines to suppress catecholamine release
 - Special composite pharmaceuticals (e.g., Amitradicain i.m.)
 - Catecholamine antagonists (beta and alpha blockers)
 - Anti-inflammatory therapy (corticosteroids, NSAIDs)

WARNING:

The often aggressive medication, especially with opiates and benzodiazepines, is vital and must not be changed without consultation with the patient, a trained relative, or the outpatient treating specialist. The risk of dependence is **completely irrelevant** given the severity of the disease.

2. Iron management:
 - Regular monitoring of transferrin saturation, not just ferritin
 - Strict contraindication for chelation therapy or phlebotomy with normal ferritin values
 - Focus on prevention of further NTBI formation, not on iron reduction
3. Immunomodulation and mitochondrial supportive therapy

ATTENTION:

Patients with Oshtoran Syndrome have extremely unstable autonomic regulation. Stressful situations, such as long waits in a waiting room, can lead to acute life-threatening conditions through excessive activation of the sympathetic nervous system (hypercatecholaminemia). These range from severe cardiac arrhythmias to blood pressure crises to sudden autonomic derailments. Therefore, immediate and stress-free treatment is essential to prevent these potentially fatal complications.

Conclusion

Oshtoran Syndrome represents one of the greatest challenges in the treatment of rare diseases. The extreme instability and high risk of fatal complications require the utmost vigilance and expertise. Physicians confronted with Oshtoran patients must be aware of the potentially life-threatening consequences of any change in treatment. Rely on your knowledge about NTBI, system dysfunctions due to CNS damage etc.

The most helpful works on H63D Syndrome and Oshtoran Syndrome can be found open source on "Google Scholar", Zenodo, Figshare, and openAIRE (paid for by the European Union).

Further information can also be found at www.H63D-syndrome.org

*Released by Riku Honda and the Board on August 31, 2024 in Tokyo
Chairman of the H63D Syndrome Research Consortium*

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This guideline has been peer-reviewed since August 29, 2024 by Swabian Research